

Movie Recommendation System Using Content-Based Filtering And Cosine Similarity

Aleena Joseph
PG Student
Dept. of computer Applications
Amal Jyothi college of Engineering
Kanjirappally, Kottayam
aleenamariya2@gmail.com

Ms. Jetty Benjamin
Asst. Professor
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi college of Engineering
Kanjirappally, Kottayam
jettybenjamin@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— By acquiring a deeper understanding of the user's preferences, recommendation systems are utilized to boost user appeal. These systems have grown in popularity as a result of their capacity to provide users with customized material that is relevant to the interests of them. The implementation of these systems can be done by collaborative filtering ,hybrid models, content-based, and also by neural networks. The goal of this research is to see if the machine learning approaches like Content-based filtering and Cosine similarity can be used to detect content similarities and suggest related movies. Cosine similarity and Euclidean distance are two ways to find similarity in genres. We have used the many metrics that are used to compute similarity between products/movies in this study.

Keywords: Content-based filtering ,collaborative filtering and cosine similarity.

I. INTRODUCTION

There are a variety of programmes that allow websites to forecast their visitors' likes and dislikes. This helps them to share the things they appreciate with others. Recommender systems propose or suggest products and ideas that are related to a user's individual way of thinking. The basic goal of recommendation systems is to suggest appropriate objects to a customer based solely on historical data. If a customer who also saw the movie you're watching right now gave it a high rating, it's considerably more likely to show in the suggestions.

By this paper the recommender suggesting movies to the users ,by comparing the preferences and genres with others. This paper mainly focused on suggesting the best movies to the users with the help of Similarity matrix and Sparse matrix, and also by the Content-based algorithm. In this paper recommending movies to the users by comparing the contents of genres in the dataset movies.csv. While watching a movie the recommender will suggest other movies which has the same contents.

Here we use mainly two machine learning approaches for finding similar content movies ,that's are content-based and cosine-similarity. Euclidean distance and cosine similarity are used to determine the degree of similarity. In cosine-

similarity, it is used to checking the similarity in the textual data. Here for doing this ,first wants to divert the data which is the textual form to the form of vector. After the conversion is done, then checking the cosine angle between if the angle between two vectors is 0. It either indicates they're comparable or they're not.

For filtering the contents we can use two filtering models; first one is content-based filtering . The obtained data is utilized to recommend articles in this filtering model, which profiles consumers based on the type of information they are interested in. The second one is collaborative filtering ,in this where we group users who are similar and use that data to make recommendations. Our motive is to provide recommendation of movies in simplest way.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

This section reviews some papers related to similar studies and are reviewed. The recommender collects the history about the behaviour ,ratings and personal interests of users. And then recommends similar results. Personalized recommender filtering the information about preferences of users [1]. With the use of Knn and collaborative filtering, authors Bei-Bei developed a system that suggests the best suggestions to users based on their preferences from a large list of movies.

Ramni Harbir Singh Et al proposed “ Movie Recommendation System using Cosine Similarity and KNN-[June-2020]” [2]. Authors attempted to increase accuracy for recommending movies. The recommender systems are in two ways; Content-based recommendation and Collaborative Filtering. Collaborative filtering is based on the notion that people with similar interests have comparable preferences. A content-based approach suggests things to customers that are related to items that the customer has previously rated highly.

M. Chenna Keshava Et al proposed “Machine Learning Model for Movie Recommendation System [April-2020]” [3]. The primary purpose of recommendation systems is to provide customers with acceptable objects based simply on previous data. If a customer who also saw the movie you're watching right now gave it a high rating, it's

considerably more likely to show in suggestions. Films with the greatest overall scores are likely to appeal to a wide range of audiences. You will learn how to develop and implement a movie recommendation machine prototype that incorporates real-world movie suggestions as well as KNN and collaborative filtering methods in this paper.

Movie recommendation using collaborative filtering was proposed by Kalp Devanshu Panwala in [4]. Recommender systems main motive is to predict user's interests and recommend product items that they may find interesting. The author used content-based and collaborative filtering for filter and recommending movies.

Poonam Sharma and Lokesh Yadav's suggested Movie Recommendation System Using Item Based Collaborative Filtering[2020][5] uses collaborative filtering to construct a recommender system. Customers are targeted based on the genre of films they prefer. The use of personalised recommendation engines is beneficial. The most common methods for offering recommendations to users are collaborative filtering and content-based filtering.

III. RECOMMENDATION SYSTEM

Based on the user's choices, a recommender system tries to forecast or filter preferences. Search queries, books, research articles, movies, music, news, social tagging, music, and general merchandise are all examples of applications where recommender systems are employed. A movie recommendation system is a fancy term for a technique that attempts to anticipate your chosen goods based on your or similar people's preferences. The fundamental goal of recommender systems is to forecast users' interests and suggest products that they would like. They're one of the most sophisticated machine learning algorithms used by internet businesses to boost sales. Data for recommender systems comes from explicit user evaluations after watching a movie or noting a song, through implicit program searches and purchase histories, or from other information regarding the users/items.

From the standpoint of the user, they are tailored to meet the user's needs in the quickest time possible. From the perspective of an organization, they want to keep the user on the platform for as long as possible so that they may make the most money possible. As a result, recommendation systems are becoming more important. The recommender system can design based on three ways. First with Content-based filtering, this mechanism gives suggestions by processing and filtering the item data. Secondly, the Collaborative filtering were dealing user data. Based on it suggests movies to users. The last one is the combination of both, that is Hybrid Recommendations.

Figure.1: Recommender System

Figure.1.1: Collaborative Filtering

Figure.1.2: Content-Based Filtering

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Source

In this paper we used movies.csv for getting data to comparing the contents with others,for recommending movies. The movies.csv dataset is taken from kaggle. This dataset mainly contains 3 features:

1. movieid: This feature describes the unique ids of movies
2. title: Title feature is the original name of the movies.
3. genre: genre feature describes the category of movies.

B. Content-Based Filtering

Similarities in products, services, or content features, as well as information obtained about the consumer, are used to produce suggestions using content-based filtering. Content-based filtering is a form of recommender system that tries to forecast what a user will like based on their past behaviour. It suggests other goods that are comparable to what the user likes based on their previous actions or explicit input.

To begin making recommendations, no data from other users is required. Content-based recommenders can be highly personalised to the user's interests, including specialised item recommendations, because the method focuses on matching the features or attributes of a database object with the user's profile. The recommendations are shown to the user. In general, content-based filtering systems are simpler to implement. When compared to collaborative filtering systems designed to mimic user-to-user recommendations, the data science behind a content-based filtering system is relatively simple. Assigning attributes is the real work in content-based filtering.

Algorithm for this method is shown below as Algorithm 1.

a) *Algorithm 1.* Movie recommendation using Content-Based filtering. Input: movies dataset. Output: Processing input data and analysing the genres content.

Step 1: Read the dataset.

Step 2: Display the contents of movies dataset

Step 3: Find the null values contained in the dataset and remove them

Step 4: Analysing the genres content.

b) *Experimental Results:* Using the content-based filtering it will filter the data based on the contents of the feature genres. It will categorise the movies by the terms of

same.genres.

Figure.2: Processing dataset

C. Cosine Similarity

The main fundamental in the Content-based is the similarity between the contents. For finding the similarity we use two mechanisms:

- 1) **Euclidean Distance:**
It is commonly used similarity distance measure and it will measure the distance between two items.

$$d(x,y) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - y_i)^2}$$

Figure.3: Equation for Euclidean Distance

- 2) **Cosine Similarity:**
The cosine of the angle between two vectors in a multidimensional space is used to calculate similarity.

$$\text{similarity}(x,y) = \cos(\theta) = \frac{x \cdot y}{|x||y|}$$

Figure.4: Equation for Cosine Similarity

In cosine-similarity it is used for checking the similarity in the textual data. Here for doing this, first wants to convert the data which is in textual form to the form of vector. After the conversion is done, then checking the cosine angle between if the angle between two vectors is 0. It either indicates they're comparable or they're not.

a) *Algorithm 1.* Movie recommendation using Cosine Similarity. Input: movies dataset. Output: Finding similarity between the feature genres and recommending similar movies .

Step 1: Input: movies data set.

Step 2: Output: Showing similar content movies.

Step 3: Input the data set.

Step 4: Convert the textual formed data to vector form.

Step 5: Using Cosine similarity checking which movies are in same content.

Step 6: Compute 10 similar movies for 3 movies.

b) *Experimental Results: Recommending 10 similar content movies for three different movies.*

```

from sklearn.feature_extraction.text import TfidfVectorizer

tf = TfidfVectorizer(analyzer='word', ngram_range=(1, 3), min_df=0, stop_words='english')

matrix = tf.fit_transform(df['genres'])

[ ] from sklearn.metrics.pairwise import linear_kernel

cosine_similarities = linear_kernel(matrix,matrix)

[ ] movie_title = df['title']

indices = pd.Series(df.index, index=df['title'])

def movie_recommend(title):

    idx = indices[title]

    sim_scores = list(enumerate(cosine_similarities[idx]))

    sim_scores = sorted(sim_scores, key=lambda x: x[1], reverse=True)

    sim_scores = sim_scores[1:31]

    movie_indices = [i[0] for i in sim_scores]

    return movie_title.iloc[movie_indices]

movie_recommend("Toy Story").head(10)
    
```

Figure.5: Checking Similarity

V. CONCLUSION

By using content-based filtering in the movie recommendation system, we were able to demonstrate how to build a movie recommendation system. A recommender system has grown increasingly important as a result of the information overload. We're trying to come up with a new way to improve the accuracy of a content-based recommender system's movie representation. To solve the issues we identified at the outset, we first construct a content-

based recommender algorithm that eliminates the need for a cold start. In this study, we use content-based filtering and cosine similarity to find movies with similar content.

```

[ ] movie_recommend('Jumanji (1995)').head(10)

53          Indian in the Cupboard, The (1995)
109         NeverEnding Story III, The (1994)
767          Escape to Witch Mountain (1975)
1514         Darby O'Gill and the Little People (1959)
1556          Return to Oz (1985)
1617         NeverEnding Story, The (1984)
1618         NeverEnding Story II: The Next Chapter, The (1...
1799          Santa Claus: The Movie (1985)
3574         Harry Potter and the Sorcerer's Stone (a.k.a. ...
6075         Chronicles of Narnia: The Lion, the Witch and ...
Name: title, dtype: object

[ ] movie_recommend('Father of the Bride Part II (1995)').head(10)

17          Four Rooms (1995)
18         Ace Ventura: When Nature Calls (1995)
58          Bio-Dome (1996)
61          Friday (1995)
79          Black Sheep (1996)
90          Mr. Wrong (1996)
92          Happy Gilmore (1996)
104         Steal Big, Steal Little (1995)
108         Flirting With Disaster (1996)
113         Down Periscope (1996)
Name: title, dtype: object

[ ] movie_recommend('Flint (2017)').head(10)

25          Othello (1995)
30          Dangerous Minds (1995)
36          Cry, the Beloved Country (1995)
39          Restoration (1995)
50          Georgia (1995)
51          Home for the Holidays (1995)
55          Mr. Holland's Opus (1995)
105         Boys of St. Vincent, The (1992)
120         Basketball Diaries, The (1995)
121         Awfully Big Adventure, An (1995)
Name: title, dtype: object
    
```

Figure.6: Result for implementation

REFERENCES

- [1] Bei-Bei CUI School of Software Engineering, Beijing University of Technology, Beijing, China, "Design and Implementation of Movie Recommendation System Based on Knn Collaborative Filtering Algorithm [2017]."
- [2] Ramni Harbir Singh, Sargam Maurya, Tanisha Tripathi, Tushar Narula, Gaurav Srivastav," Movie Recommendation System using Cosine Similarity and KNN-[June-2020].",
- [3] M.Chenna Keshava , S. Srinivasulu, P. Narendra Reddy, B. DineshNaik "Machine Learning Model for Movie Recommendation System. [April-2020]" .
- [4] Kalp DevanshuPanwala," Movies Recommendation System. [2020] "
- [5] Poonam Sharma, Lokesh Yadav, "Movie Recommendation System Using Item Based Collaborative Filtering [2020] ."